

One pot synthesis of cobalt ferrites nanoparticles via hydrothermal method and their optical studies

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Abstract : Well dispersed spinel cobalt ferrite nanoparticles have been synthesized successfully through hydrothermal method in one step. The structure, morphology and properties of the nanoparticles were characterized by X-ray diffraction, transmission electron microscopy and ultraviolet-visible spectroscopy. Transmission electron microscopic studies show that spinel cobalt ferrite nanoparticles are uniform with an average size of 10–15.7 nm. The optical band gap are equal to 2.3, 2.35 and 2.4 eV for CoFe₂O₄ obtained by using UV-Visible spectroscopy which may have visible-light photo activity.

Keywords : Cobalt ferrite, nanoparticles, spinel, transmission electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction, optical properties.

Introduction

In the past few decades, the nanostructured spinel ferrites (MFe₂O₄) have been attracted many researchers due to their unique physical and chemical properties¹. These materials are promising for catalysis², magnetisms³, magnetic biomedicines⁴, adsorption⁵, gas-sensor⁶, electrode materials⁷ and environmental remediation⁸. However, among spinel ferrites, cobalt ferrite (CoFe₂O₄) is an excellent material for its applications in electronics such as computers, recording devices and magnetic cards, which is due to its high electromagnetic performance, high coercivity, moderate saturation magnetization, chemical stability and mechanical hardness^{9,10}. Spinel ferrite nanoparticles also have some potential biological applications, such as magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), magnetic fluid hyperthermia (MFH), magnetic separations, biosensors, targeted and controlled drug delivery^{11–15}.

Synthesis of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles with the de-

sired physical and chemical properties are very important area of research and development. To date, many methods like ceramic¹⁶, co-precipitation^{16–18}, ball milling¹⁶, reverse micelles¹⁹, sol-gel²⁰, laser ablation²¹, polyol²², sonochemical²³, aerosol synthesis²⁴, polymeric precursor²⁵ and hydrothermal methods^{26,27} have been used for the synthesis of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles. However, most of these methods used expensive chemicals and toxic reagents which may be harmful to the environment. Among these synthetic methods, hydrothermal method is inexpensive, reduce the synthesis time and provide the homogeneous almost regular cubic shape and high purity. Due to this reason we use the hydrothermal method for the synthesis of spinel cobalt ferrite nanoparticles. To the best of our knowledge, there are only few reports on one step synthesis of spinel cobalt ferrite nanoparticles^{28–30}.

In the present paper, we are reporting first time the one pot synthesis, characterization and effect of polysac-

charides (cellulose and starch) on morphology and optical studies of spinel cobalt ferrite nanoparticles by using hydrothermal method.

Results and discussion

The XRD patterns of the as synthesized samples (HT-1a, HT-1b and HT-1c) have been shown in Fig. 1 to identify the effect of two different polysaccharides. Our results, exhibits (111), (220), (311), (222), (400), (422),

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction patterns of CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles prepared by hydrothermal method : (a) HT-1a (without polysaccharide), (b) HT-1b (with cellulose) and (c) HT-1c (starch).

(511) and (440) planes, which confirm the formation of monophasic spinel cobalt ferrite nanoparticles with a face-centered cubic structure (space group $\text{Fd-}3\text{m}$, JCPDS card no. 22-1086)²⁸. It is clearly seen from the figure that there is no other reflection is observed corresponded to any kind of impurities. This suggests that nano-sized cobalt ferrites have been prepared in only one step without calcination. Bragg's law was used to calculate Interplaner distances (d_{hkl}). The crystallite size (d) and lattice constant (a) of cobalt ferrites were calculated from the most intense peak (311), using the Debye-Scherrer formula :

stant (a) of cobalt ferrites were calculated from the most intense peak (311), using the Debye-Scherrer formula :

$$d = 0.9 \lambda / \beta \cos \theta$$

where, λ is the wavelength of X-ray ($\text{Cu-K}\alpha = 0.154$ nm), d is the size of crystallite (nm), β is the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of prominent intense peak measured in radians, and θ is peak angle³¹. The lattice constant (a), Interplaner spacing (d), X-ray density (d_x) and crystallite size (d) are shown in Table 1. The XRD results revealed that the spinel CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles showed smallest size in starch and largest without polysaccharide.

Fig. 2 shows the EDX spectrum of as prepared nano cobalt ferrites (HT-1a, HT-1b and HT-1c) which confirm that only Fe, Co and oxygen elements are present. Thus, it is also confirmed from EDX analysis that nano-sized cobalt ferrites were formed in only one step. The EDX analysis showed that the experimental loaded composition of nano ferrite is corroborated well with the theoretical ratio as shown in Table 2 which corresponds to the formation of monophasic products.

In order to understand the effect of cellulose and starch on the final products, the microscopic experiments were performed at same condition. The TEM images of as prepared spinel cobalt ferrites nanoparticles (HT-1a, HT-1b and HT-1c) are shown in Fig. 3, which showed the formation of nearly regular and cuboidal shaped ferrite nanostructures. There is almost no effect of polysaccharides on the morphology but smallest size of 10 nm with starch and large size of 15.7 nm without polysaccharide was observed. The grain size of the spinel cobalt ferrites nanoparticles obtained from TEM studies was in close agreement with the X-ray size obtained from the Scherrer's equation using X-ray line broadening studies.

The UV-Visible spectra of spinel cobalt ferrite nanoparticles prepared by hydrothermal method are shown in Fig. 4. It is well known that the optical band gap (E_g) can be achieved by the following equation :

$$(A h\nu)^n = B(h\nu - E_g)$$

Table 1. Data of crystallite size, inter-planer spacing, lattice constant and X-ray density of CoFe_2O_4 samples

Sample	Position of 311 peak (degree)	Crystallite size (XRD; nm)	Interplaner spacing (d_{311} ; nm)	Lattice constant (a ; nm)	Density (d_x ; g/cm^3)
HT-1a	35.449	13.54	0.2532	0.839	5.27
HT-1b	35.560	13.06	0.2524	0.837	5.31
HT-1c	35.382	12.65	0.2536	0.841	5.23

Fig. 2. EDX of as prepared CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles : (a) HT-1a, (b) HT-1b and (c) HT-1c.

Table 2. EDX analysis results of metal ratios in the resultant samples

Sample code	Elements	Original ratio	Atomic weight (%)	Detected ratio
HT-1a	Co	$\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+} = 0.5$	14.24	$\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+} = 0.49$
	Fe		29.01	
HT-1b	Co	$\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+} = 0.5$	13.30	$\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+} = 0.45$
	Fe		29.14	
HT-1c	Co	$\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+} = 0.5$	11.39	$\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Fe}^{3+} = 0.47$
	Fe		23.95	

where $h\nu$ is the photon energy; A is absorbance, B is a constant related to the material; and n indicates either 2 or $\frac{1}{2}$ for direct transition and indirect transition, respectively³². Hence, the optical band gap for the absorption peak can be obtained by extrapolating the linear portion of the $(Ah\nu)^n - h\nu$ curve to zero^{33,34}. Insets of Fig. 4 show the $(Ah\nu)^2$ versus $h\nu$ curve for the sample. The curves indicate that the values of the direct band gap (E_g)

are equal to 2.3, 2.35 and 2.4 eV for CoFe_2O_4 from the intercept of the tangent to the line, which corresponds to the CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles may have visible-light photo activity. In order to understand the influence of polysaccharides (starch and cellulose), there is little bit effect of polysaccharides in their energy band gap as the direct band gap is marginally changes from 2.35 to 2.4 eV. The

Fig. 3. TEM images of as prepared CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles : (a) HT-1a, (b) HT-1b and (c) HT-1c.

slight variation in the band gap may be associated due to the structural similarity between cellulose and starch.

Experimental

Materials :

All the reagents used in this work, including cobalt chloride [CoCl₂·6H₂O], ferric chloride [FeCl₃·6H₂O], sodium hydroxide [NaOH], starch and cellulose are analytical grade and used as received without further purification. 100 mL of 0.6 molar solution of ferric chloride, 100 mL of 0.3 molar solution cobalt chloride and 50 mL of 3 molar solution of NaOH were prepared in double distilled water.

Synthetic procedure :

In a typical synthesis, 25 ml of 0.6 molar ferric chloride hexahydrate (FeCl₃·6H₂O) was taken in a Teflon lined vessel to which 25 ml of 0.3 molar cobalt chloride hexahydrate (CoCl₂·6H₂O) was added. Then 25 ml of 3 molar NaOH was added dropwise into the above solution to increase the pH of the solution. The final solution was

sealed and heated in a hydrothermal Parr reactor 4848 at 100 °C for 2 h, then allowed to cool at room temperature naturally. After completing the reaction, black colored precipitates were obtained which was collected by centrifugation and washed with deionized water several times until pH become neutral, then dried overnight in an oven at 110 °C to get CoFe₂O₄ nanoparticles. The prepared product was abbreviated by HT-1a.

We obtained second and third sample (HT-1b and HT-1c) by same procedure in which 2 g cellulose and 2 g starch along with sodium hydroxide solution was added respectively.

Instrumental techniques :

The crystal structures were analyzed by X-ray diffraction (XRD, Philips PW3040/60) equipped with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). XRD patterns were collected at room temperature using a continuous scan over an angular range of $2\theta = 10^\circ - 70^\circ$ with step size of 0.02° and scan rate of 2° min^{-1} . The morphology of the synthesized cobalt ferrite nanoparticles was characterized by

Fig. 4. UV-Vis absorption spectrum and plots of $(Ah\nu)^n$ as a function of photon energy ($h\nu$) for as prepared CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles : (a) HT-1a, (b) HT-1b and (c) HT-1c.

using Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) on a JEOL 2100F operated at 200 kV. UV-Visible absorption spectra were recorded using Shimadzu 1601PC UV-Visible double-beam spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 290–800 nm.

Conclusion

Nearly regular and cuboidal spinel structures (10–15.7 nm) of cobalt ferrite have been synthesized through hydrothermal method at 100 °C in one step. EDX and XRD results show the high purity of cobalt ferrites. The grain size of cobalt ferrite nanoparticles is in close agreement with the TEM and XRD studies. UV-Visible studies show the optical band gaps of 2.3, 2.35 and 2.4 eV, which indicates CoFe_2O_4 nanoparticles may have visible-light photo activity. This method does not require any complex apparatus, catalyst or any surfactants. This method could also be extended for the formation of other metal oxide nanoparticles.

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